

The Association Between (Blood) Biomarkers and Pulmonary Disease in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: Protocol for a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Observational Studies

Authors/Collaborators (order TBD)

Henrik Z Langkilde (HZL), MD¹, Jesper R Davidsen (JRD), MD, PhD^{2,3}, Stefan MW Harders (SMWH), MD, PhD⁴, Sanjeewa Patabendige (SP), MD^{2,3}, Christine Nilsson (CN), MD⁵, Elisabet Svenungsson (ES), MD, PhD⁶, Zahi Touma (ZT), MD, PhD⁷, Sille Fløjborg (SF), AP⁸, Robin Christensen (RC), BSc, MSc, PhD^{4,9}, and Anne Voss (AV), MD, PhD¹.

Affiliations

- 1: Research Unit of Rheumatology, Department of Clinical Research, University of Southern Denmark, Odense University Hospital, Denmark.
- 2: Research Unit of Respiratory Medicine, Department of Clinical Research, University of Southern Denmark, Odense University Hospital, Denmark.
- 3: South Danish Center for Interstitial Lung Diseases (SCILS) and Pulmo-Rheuma Frontline Center (PURE), Department of Respiratory Medicine, Odense University Hospital, Odense, Denmark.
- 4: Research Unit of Department of Radiology, University of Southern Denmark, Odense University Hospital, Denmark.
- 5: Research Unit of Department of Clinical Immunology, University of Southern Denmark, Odense University Hospital, Denmark.
- 6: Department of Medicine Solna, Division of Rheumatology, Karolinska Institute, Karolinska University Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden.
- 7: Division of Rheumatology, Department of Medicine, Toronto Western Hospital, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada.
- 8: Systemic Lupus Erythematosus Patient Research Partner, Department of Rheumatology, Odense University Hospital, Denmark
- 9: Section for Biostatistics and Evidence-Based Research, the Parker Institute, Copenhagen University Hospital, Bispebjerg and Frederiksberg, Copenhagen, Denmark.

Corresponding author.

Henrik Zachar Langkilde MD, PhD Fellow (ORCID ID 0000-0002-3700-0755)

Department of Rheumatology, Odense University Hospital

J.B. Winsløws Vej 4, 5000 Odense C, Denmark

E-mail: Henrik.zachar.langkilde@rsyd.dk telephone +45 6126 8754

2023, 11th December

First edition: 2023, 30th November.

In accordance with the PRISMA-P guidelines, this systematic review protocol will be registered with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) before initiating the search etc. If the protocol needs amendments, we will state the reason why, the date and describe the change.

Contributions:

HZL is the guarantor and developer of the protocol. He will perform the search, screen the articles and draft the manuscript. A health science librarian helped developing the search strings. All authors contributed to the development of the selection criteria and commented on the protocol.

HZL and SP will evaluate if articles meet the eligibility criteria, perform data extraction and evaluate bias, when disagreement AV will settle them.

JRD and SP provide expertise on respiratory medicine, SMWH provides expertise on radiology, CN provides expertise on immunology, ES provides expertise on systemic lupus erythematosus and the association to biomarkers, ZT provides methodical expertise and expertise on systemic lupus erythematosus, SF provides the patient's perspective, RC provides methodical and biostatistical expertise, AV provides expertise on systemic lupus erythematosus and supervises the process. All authors read the protocol, provided feedback, and approved the final protocol manuscript.

SUMMARY

Background

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is an autoimmune disease that potentially can affect any organ. Pulmonary disease is common among SLE patients and is associated with further morbidity, reduced health related quality of life, and mortality. The diagnose of pulmonary disease in patients with SLE can be challenging, thus, diagnostically, supportive biomarkers are urgently needed.

Objective

To use a systematic review approach with evidence synthesis, to identify available biomarkers that have been associated with either presence (yes/no) and/or severity (a degree) of pulmonary disease among SLE patients.

Methods and Analysis

The protocol is developed and reported in accordance with the PRISMA-P reporting guideline. We will include observational studies (i.e., both longitudinal and cross-sectional studies), that meet the following STARD eligibility criteria:

- Patients: SLE patients
- Index test: Circulating biomarkers
- Comparison: Reference standard (Presence and/or severity of pulmonary disease)
- Outcome: Association measures reported in the individual studies

We will search Embase (OVID), MEDLINE (OVID) and Web of Science for eligible study. Studies will be screened on basis of title and abstract. Possible eligible studies will be retrieved in full text and evaluated. Results including associations between measures will be recorded in a customised (pre-specified) Excel spread sheet.

For each association, we will prepare a quantitative evidence synthesis when possible (e.g., when available from at least two studies). We also aim to combine individual study results (associations) with a quantitative evidence synthesis (i.e., meta-analysis) section, if the studies are sufficiently homogeneous. We will use the result of the Fisher-transformation of a correlation coefficient r with the corresponding standard error in all meta-analyses. We will investigate heterogeneity by Forest plots and I^2 tests.

Discussion

We believe that the results could guide clinicians when selecting biomarkers to screen for and diagnose pulmonary disease in SLE patients. This could help clinicians to detect and triage the diagnosis of pulmonary disease among SLE patients.

Registration

The study registered at PROSPERO on 2023-11-27, ID CRD 42023394680.

INTRODUCTION

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is an autoimmune disease defined by the presence of antinuclear antibodies and characteristic involvement of several organs, causing increased morbidity, mortality, and reduced health related quality of life. SLE is commonly associated with haematological abnormalities, rashes, arthralgia/ arthritis, nephritis, and constitutional symptoms (1, 2).

Pulmonary diseases among SLE patients are common. An autopsy study report that 97% of all deceased SLE patients had signs of pulmonary involvement (3), while another autopsy study suggested, that a part of the pulmonary changes can be attributed to other causes apart from SLE such as infections and aspiration (4). Attempts have been made to estimate the prevalence of pulmonary disease among SLE patients, but mostly in tertiary centres (5). The prevalence of SLE related pulmonary disease have been reported to be approximately 50% depending on geographical location and definition of pulmonary disease (5, 6). Presence of pulmonary diseases are associated to a significantly increased mortality (7). Osman et. al. have associated pulmonary disease among SLE patients to a lower self-reported health related quality of life (8). Unfortunately, there is a big discrepancy between how clinicians assess and grade pulmonary disease among SLE patients and how patients experience it (9). Importantly, if pulmonary disease is diagnosed in SLE patients it will often prompt treatment or lead to change in existing treatment options (10).

Diagnosing SLE-related pulmonary disease can be cumbersome and will in many instances require specialised tests and staff (11), making it challenging to participate in the diagnostic program for SLE patients who suffer from severe fatigue and cognitive dysfunction (12) and not available in places with limited resources. Associations between certain biomarkers and pulmonary disease among SLE patients have been identified in several studies (11, 13-15), but to our knowledge the existing knowledge has never been addressed by a systematic review.

Rationale for this evidence synthesis study

Pulmonary disease is common among SLE patients, and it is associated to increased mortality, morbidity, and reduced health related quality of life, but to date it draws little attention, maybe because of the insidious nature of these symptoms. We hypothesise that new biomarkers can help diagnose pulmonary disease among SLE patients, which will make diagnostics more accessible, but also detect pulmonary disease earlier in well-selected SLE patients. Blood samples and analyses of common circulating biomarkers are already incorporated as a central part of everyday clinical practice by many rheumatologists; thus, it would be easy to adapt screening of circulating biomarkers, in SLE patients suspected of pulmonary disease. We believe that a systematic review focused on the association between circulating biomarkers and presence (screening/diagnostic) and/or severity of pulmonary disease among SLE patients (descriptive) will help guide clinicians to choose which circulating biomarkers to use when screening SLE patients for pulmonary disease or evaluating the severity of pulmonary disease.

Evidence-based research: We performed a pragmatic search for previous systematic reviews on 20. June 2023 reporting on circulating biomarkers, lung disease, and SLE:

(SLE[tiab] OR lupus[tiab] OR "systemic lupus erythematosus"[tiab])

AND

(ILD[tiab] OR "interstitial lung disease"[tiab] OR lung*[tiab] OR pulmon*[tiab] OR respiratory[tiab])

AND

"systematic review"[pt]

This search generated 57 potentially relevant review papers that were scrutinised. None reported on the combination of circulating biomarkers, and lung diseases in patients with SLE in clinical research projects (list of references in the end of the protocol).

Purpose of this systematic review

The aim of this systematic review is to evaluate if any circulating biomarkers can be used to help screen and diagnose pulmonary disease among SLE patients and discriminate between different pulmonary diseases, and if so, which circulating biomarkers. This is done by reviewing cross-sectional and longitudinal clinical studies that assess the association between presence and/or severity of pulmonary disease and autoantibodies, cytokines and selected other circulating biomarkers, from henceforth referred to as circulating biomarkers.

The systematic review will address the following research questions:

- Are circulating biomarkers in general associated with presence (yes/no) and/or severity (scale) of pulmonary disease among SLE patients?
- Are certain circulating biomarkers associated with presence and/or severity of specific pulmonary diseases among SLE patients?

Patient perspective

The protocol is discussed with a patient partner (SF). SF approves the protocol and claims that it is a clinically relevant and important project.

METHODS

Protocol and registration

The protocol is reported in accordance with the "Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols" (PRISMA-P) (16) guidelines, and it is registered with the

International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) on 2023-11-27, ID CRD42023394680.

Eligibility

Studies will be included if they meet the following criteria:

- Study design: Cross-sectional and longitudinal studies. The presence of pulmonary disease must be evaluated clinically and not by register data or by damage score
- Patients: Humans with the condition of interest = Individuals with the diagnosis Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, and fulfilling the relevant classification criteria, at the time of study
- Index test: Studies addressing the presence of circulating biomarkers (autoantibodies and/or cytokines and/or selected other biomarker)
- Comparison: Reference standard and the reported presence and/or severity of pulmonary disease, but not pulmonary arterial hypertension or thromboembolic disease such as pulmonary embolism
- Outcome: Association between reported index test and comparison in the individual studies

We will have no restriction on setting; but we demand that the pulmonary diseases among SLE patients are diagnosed in a clinical study, hence the participants diagnose is not derived from a damage or activity score. The reason for this choice is, that we suspect that a certain proportion of pulmonary disease is un-diagnosed among SLE patients. This is exemplified by Narváez et al. who reported that 31% of SLE patients had a pulmonary disease (7) while autopsy studies suggested that 97% of SLE patients had a pulmonary disease (3). We will include abstracts and letters if they can provide relevant knowledge. We only include studies reported in English. A list of possible relevant titles in other languages will be provided in an appendix following the final manuscript.

Information sources and Search strategy

Literature search will be developed using subject headings and free text search terms related to our research questions in collaboration with a Health Sciences Librarian and all authors are asked to comment on the final search strings. We plan to search Embase (OVID) and MEDLINE (OVID). HZL will perform forward, and backward citation search based on articles gained from the original search in Web of Science. All authors will report extra studies if they know about relevant studies. There is no limit in regards of data coverage. No study design, date or language limits will be imposed to the search. Only studies in other languages than English that can be translated adequately using Google translate will be included due to resource limits. A list of possible relevant studies in other languages that cannot be adequately translated will be provided in the final manuscript.

Study selection

Literature search results will be uploaded and sorted in the article management tool Covidence. Duplicates will be removed by Covidence, and afterwards by HZL. HZL will screen the generated titles and abstracts when necessary, according to eligibility criteria. The remaining studies or studies where there is a doubt will be evaluated in full text according to the eligibility criteria by HZL and SP separately and blinded to each other's results. If necessary, we will ask authors of original studies to provide additional information to evaluate if the studies meet the eligibility criteria. Disagreements will be settled through a discussion moderated by AV. Reasons for excluding full text reviewed studies will be reported in an appendix after the final manuscript. For the selection of studies, see outline for the flow diagram in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Flow diagram

Data collection

HZL and SP will separately and blinded to each other extract data to a customised (pre-specified) Excel spreadsheet including information about demography, methodology, interventions, and

patient outcomes. Disagreements will be settled in a discussion including HZL, SP and AV. If data is not written in the text, we will try extract data from tables and figures. If all data from a study is not published, we will contact the author (with a maximum of three mails) to supply additional information. If we find multiple reports on the same study, we will only include the study once and we will select the publication with the most comprehensive data.

Data items

We will extract following items see below. If missing data authors will be contacted. If we cannot get the data, it will be noted in final publication.

- Regarding studies: Author, the year the study was performed, year the study was published, reference, type of study, country, inclusion period, number of centres, investigated test, reference, funding, and publication status. Time between reference and investigated test
- Regarding study population: Inclusion and exclusion criteria, number of patients, and selected characteristic – sex, age, activity index scores, damage index scores, smoking status, treatment.
- Results: Investigated autoantibody and/or cytokine and/or other biomarker and if possible, antibody strength and cytokine/biomarker levels. Possible antibodies, cytokines, and other biomarkers are listed in table 1. Pulmonary disease, sub-classified (if possible pulmonary disease will be sub-classified we will record the diagnosis (pleural affection, interstitial lung disease, vasculitis, pulmonary haemorrhage, and the syndrome “shrinking lung syndrome”, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Asthma)), how patients were diagnosed, reason for dropout, type of radiological evaluation (High Resolution Computed Tomography of Thorax, Computed Tomography of Thorax, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Positron Emission Tomography, Chest X-ray), radiological findings, and results from pulmonary function tests (Forces Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV₁), FEV₁/FVC, Total Lung Capacity (TLC), Diffusion Capacity (DLCO), Residual Volume (RV), and Carbon Monoxide Transfer Coefficient (KCO). Associations between autoantibody and/or cytokine and/or other biomarker and prevalence and/or severity of pulmonary disease (Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, true positive, false positive, false negative, true negative).

The major outcome is: The association between pulmonary diseases and circulating biomarkers, see **Table 1**.

Minor outcomes are:

- The association between circulating biomarkers and specific pulmonary diseases (pleural affection, interstitial lung disease, vasculitis, pulmonary haemorrhage, the syndrome “shrinking lung syndrome”, COPD, and Asthma), see **Table 2a**
- Antibody strength and cytokine and other biomarker level for cut-off for the association between presence of pulmonary disease and circulating biomarkers, see **Table 2b**

- The association between circulating biomarkers and results from pulmonary function tests measurements of participants (FVC, FEV₁, FEV₁/FVC, TLC, DLCO, RV, and KCO, see **Table 2c**)
- The association between circulating biomarkers and findings of radiological examinations of thorax (High Resolution Computed Tomography of Thorax, Computed Tomography of Thorax, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Positron Emission Tomography, Chest X-ray), see **Table 2d**

Risk of bias.

The risk of bias will be addressed by HZL and SP, disagreements will be settled by a discussion including AV. The QUADAS 2 tool will be used by HZL and SP, it covers patient selection, investigated test, reference test and timing of test. Studies will be graded as having a high, low or unclear risk of bias. HZL and SP will be blinded to each other results until the QUADAS 2 tool is filled out for the evaluated study. Bias will be evaluated on study level. The risk of reporting bias will be evaluated according to the ORBIT methods by HZL and SP (17).

Summary measures and Synthesis of results.

We will report study characteristics as described above. Categorical variables will be presented as absolute (n) and relative measures (%). Continuous variables will be presented with a mean, median, range, and a 95% confidence interval. No subgroup analyses are planned. If a circulating biomarker is associated with clinical outcomes in one or more studies, it will be considered a 'possible association' factor and the results were presented as part of the evidence profile. When data are available in different formats, data from the 'fully adjusted' analyses will be given preference and included in the analysis.

For each association, we will prepare a quantitative evidence synthesis. We also aim to combine individual study results (associations) with a quantitative evidence synthesis (i.e., meta-analysis) section, if the studies are sufficient homogeneous.

The principal quantitative result extracted from each study, which would form the basis for the meta-analysis, will be chosen to be as close as possible to an estimate of the target parameter; the extent to which biases would have to be assessed will likely be minimized. For example, adjusted associations will be chosen if available. Since the biomarker (X) and outcome variables (Y) will be on different scales in different studies, and because results will be presented in different formats, it will be necessary to convert all extracted results to a common scale as proposed by Thompson et. al (18). Moreover, standard errors are not easily available. Our approach will be to transform all associations into correlation coefficients using, if nothing else are available, using the sample size and the *P*-value to derive these.

We will apply the Fisher-transformation of a correlation coefficient *r* (18):

$$z = 0.5 \ln[(1 + r) / (1 - r)]$$

with the standard error of z $SE = \sqrt{1/(n - 3)}$

where n is the sample size.

Thus, the relevant (two-sided) P -value and 95% confidence interval reported in the article is converted into a standard normal score S taking due to the sign of the association in the article, the Fisher-transformed correlation derived as $z = S \times \sqrt{1/(n - 3)}$, and subsequently the results will be back-transformed as $r = (e^{2z} - 1) / (e^{2z} + 1)$. Where papers present both a correlation coefficient and a P -value, our derived correlation will be compared with the published value.

We will investigate homogeneity by a forest plot and I^2 test. The studies will be regarded heterogeneous if $I^2 \geq 50\%$. We will perform evidence synthesis if two or more studies investigate the same biomarker (X) associated with the outcome (Y) as index test and I^2 is $\leq 50\%$. If data is not suited for a meta-analysis data will be presented in a systematic narrative synthesis, including text, tables, and figures.

Data will be described, and primary outcome listed in a table with measured circulating biomarker and prevalence of pulmonary disease (table 1). If possible secondary outcomes will also be listed in separate tables (table 2a-d). All results will be reported independent of the risk of bias in each study, but we will judge the evidence accordingly.

Table 1. Association matrix: Clinical outcome and circulating biomarkers, in pulmonary diseases among SLE patients.

Biomarker	Clinical outcomes										
	LB	HRCT	CT	MRI	PET	CXR	BP	SP	MDD	CCE	Combination
Autoantibodies:											
ANA											
ANA, pattern											
dsDNA											
Smith											
SSA											
Ro 52-kDa											
Ro 60-kDa											
La (SSB)											
Histone											
ANCA											
ANCA, PR ₃											
ANCA, MPO											
p-ANCA											
c-ANCA											
GBM											
B-2 glycoprotein											
Cardiolipin											
Lupus anticoagulant											
C1q											
RNA-pol-III											
Scl-70											
IgM RF											
IgA RF											
ACPA											
Ribosomal P Protein											
U1-RNP											
ENA											
Centromere antibody											
Jo1											
Mi-2- α											
Mi-2- β											
TIF1- γ											
PM/Scl-75											
PM/Scl-100											
Ku											

PL7										
HMGCR										
NT5cl/mup4										
CENP-A										
CENP-B										
NOR90										
Th/to/hPOPI										
RNPC3										
TERF-1										
MDA5										
NXP2										
SAE1										
SRP										
PL12										
EJ										
OJ										
Ha										
Ks										
Zo										
Cytokines:										
IFN- γ										
IFN type 1										
IFN type 2										
TNF- α										
IL1										
IL2										
IL6										
IL8										
IL10										
IL12										
IL12, p70										
IL16										
IL17										
IL21										
CX3CL1										
I-TAC/CXCL11										
CCL14										
CCL21										
CCL28										
MCP-1										
MCP-4										
4BB-1										
IP10										

Others:												
Pro-BNP												
CRP												
LDH												
Complement C ₃												
Complement C _{3c}												
Complement C _{3d}												
Complement C ₄												
Complement C _{4c}												
Complement CH ₅₀												
KL-6												
SP-A												
SP-D												

LB - Lung biopsy, HRCT – High Resolution Computed Tomography of Thorax, CT - Computed Tomography of Thorax, MRI - Magnetic Resonance Imaging, PET - Positron Emission Tomography, CXR - Chest X-ray, BP - Body Plethysmography, SP - Spirometry, MDD - Multidisciplinary Discussion, CCE - Composite Clinical Evaluation, and Combination – a combination of the above mentioned modalities.

Table 2a, associations between circulating biomarkers and specific pulmonary diseases.

Biomarker	Pulmonary diseases						
	PA	ILD	Vasculitis	PH	SLS	COPD	Asthma
<i>Autoantibodies:</i>							
ANA							
ANA, pattern							
dsDNA							
Smith							
SSA							
Ro 52-kDa							
Ro 60-kDa							
La (SSB)							
Histone							
ANCA							
ANCA, PR ₃							
ANCA, MPO							
p-ANCA							
c-ANCA							
GBM							
B-2 glycoprotein							
Cardiolipin							
Lupus anticoagulant							
C1q							
RNA-pol-III							
Scl-70							
IgM RF							
IgA RF							
ACPA							
Ribosomal P Protein							
U1-RNP							
ENA							
Centromere antibody							
Jo1							
Mi-2- α							
Mi-2- β							
TIF1- γ							
PM/Scl-75							
PM/Scl-100							
Ku							
PL7							
HMGCR							

NT5cl/mup4							
CENP-A							
CENP-B							
NOR90							
Th/to/hPOPI							
RNPC3							
TERF-1							
MDA5							
NXP2							
SAE1							
SRP							
PL12							
EJ							
OJ							
Ha							
Ks							
Zo							
Cytokines:							
IFN- γ							
IFN type 1							
IFN type 2							
TNF- α							
IL1							
IL2							
IL6							
IL8							
IL10							
IL12							
IL12, p70							
IL16							
IL17							
IL21							
CX3CL1							
I-TAC/CXCL11							
CCL14							
CCL21							
CCL28							
MCP-1							
MCP-4							
4BB-1							
IP10							

Others:							
Pro-BNP							
CRP							
LDH							
Complement C ₃							
Complement C _{3c}							
Complement C _{3d}							
Complement C ₄							
Complement C _{4c}							
Complement CH ₅₀							
KL-6							
SP-A							
SP-D							

PA - pleural affection, ILD - interstitial lung disease, PH- pulmonary haemorrhage, SLS - "shrinking lung syndrome", COPD, and Asthma

Table 2b, Autoantibody strength and cytokine level for cut-off for the associations between circulating biomarkers and specific pulmonary diseases.

Biomarker and strength/level	Pulmonary diseases						
	PA	ILD	Vasculitis	PH	SLS	COPD	Asthma
Autoantibodies:							
ANA							
ANA, pattern							
dsDNA							
Smith							
SSA							
Ro 52-kDa							
Ro 60-kDa							
La (SSB)							
Histone							
ANCA							
ANCA, PR ₃							
ANCA, MPO							
p-ANCA							
c-ANCA							
GBM							
B-2 glycoprotein							
Cardiolipin							
Lupus anticoagulant							
C1q							
RNA-pol-III							
Scl-70							
IgM RF							
IgA RF							
ACPA							
Ribosomal P Protein							
U1-RNP							
ENA							
Centromere antibody							
Jo1							
Mi-2- α							
Mi-2- β							
TIF1- γ							
PM/Scl-75							
PM/Scl-100							
Ku							
PL7							

HMGCR							
NT5cl/mup4							
CENP-A							
CENP-B							
NOR90							
Th/to/hPOPI							
RNPC3							
TERF-1							
MDA5							
NXP2							
SAE1							
SRP							
PL12							
EJ							
OJ							
Ha							
Ks							
Zo							
Cytokines:							
IFN- γ							
IFN type 1							
IFN type 2							
TNF- α							
IL1							
IL2							
IL6							
IL8							
IL10							
IL12							
IL12, p70							
IL16							
IL17							
IL21							
CX3CL1							
I-TAC/CXCL11							
CCL14							
CCL21							
CCL28							
MCP-1							
MCP-4							
4BB-1							
IP10							

Others:							
Pro-BNP							
CRP							
LDH							
Complement C ₃							
Complement C _{3c}							
Complement C _{3d}							
Complement C ₄							
Complement C _{4c}							
Complement CH ₅₀							
KL-6							
SP-A							
SP-D							

PA - pleural affection, a-ILD -acute interstitial lung disease, c-ILD - interstitial lung disease a-PN - acute pneumonitis, PH-pulmonary haemorrhage, SLS - "shrinking lung syndrome", COPD, and Asthma

Table 2c, associations between circulating biomarkers and pulmonary function tests measurements.

Biomarker	Pulmonary function tests measurements.						
	FVC	FEV ₁	FEV ₁ /FVC	TLC	DLCO	RV	KCO
<i>Autoantibodies:</i>							
ANA							
ANA, pattern							
dsDNA							
Smith							
SSA							
Ro 52-kDa							
Ro 60-kDa							
La (SSB)							
Histone							
ANCA							
ANCA, PR ₃							
ANCA, MPO							
p-ANCA							
c-ANCA							
GBM							
B-2 glycoprotein							
Cardiolipin							
Lupus anticoagulant							
C1q							
RNA-pol-III							
Scl-70							
IgM RF							
IgA RF							
ACPA							
Ribosomal P Protein							
U1-RNP							
ENA							
Centromere antibody							
Jo1							
Mi-2-α							
Mi-2-β							
TIF1-γ							
PM/Scl-75							
PM/Scl-100							
Ku							
PL7							
HMGCR							
NT5cl/mup4							

CENP-A							
CENP-B							
NOR90							
Th/to/hPOPI							
RNPC3							
TERF-1							
MDA5							
NXP2							
SAE1							
SRP							
PL12							
EJ							
OJ							
Ha							
Ks							
Zo							
Cytokines:							
IFN- γ							
IFN type 1							
IFN type 2							
TNF- α							
IL1							
IL2							
IL6							
IL8							
IL10							
IL12							
IL12, p70							
IL16							
IL17							
IL21							
CX3CL1							
I-TAC/CXCL11							
CCL14							
CCL21							
CCL28							
MCP-1							
MCP-4							
4BB-1							
IP10							
Others:							
Pro-BNP							

CRP							
LDH							
Complement C ₃							
Complement C _{3c}							
Complement C _{3d}							
Complement C ₄							
Complement C _{4c}							
Complement CH ₅₀							
KL-6							
SP-A							
SP-D							

Forces Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV₁), Total Lung Capacity (TLC), Diffusion Capacity (DLCO), Residual Volume (RV), and Carbon Monoxide Transfer Coefficient (KCO)

Table 2d, associations between circulating biomarkers and findings of radiological examinations of thorax.

Biomarker	Radiological examinations of thorax				
	HRCT	CT	MRI	PET	CXR
<i>Autoantibodies:</i>					
ANA					
ANA, pattern					
dsDNA					
Smith					
SSA					
Ro 52-kDa					
Ro 60-kDa					
La (SSB)					
Histone					
ANCA					
ANCA, PR ₃					
ANCA, MPO					
p-ANCA					
c-ANCA					
GBM					
B-2 glycoprotein					
Cardiolipin					
Lupus anticoagulant					
C1q					
RNA-pol-III					
Scl-70					
IgM RF					
IgA RF					
ACPA					
Ribosomal P Protein					
U1-RNP					
ENA					
Centromere antibody					
Jo1					
Mi-2- α					
Mi-2- β					
TIF1- γ					

PM/Scl-75					
PM/Scl-100					
Ku					
PL7					
HMGCR					
NT5cl/mup4					
CENP-A					
CENP-B					
NOR90					
Th/to/hPOPI					
RNPC3					
TERF-1					
MDA5					
NXP2					
SAE1					
SRP					
PL12					
EJ					
OJ					
Ha					
Ks					
Zo					
Cytokines:					
IFN- γ					
IFN type 1					
IFN type 2					
TNF- α					
IL1					
IL2					
IL6					
IL8					
IL10					
IL12					
IL12, p70					
IL16					
IL17					
IL21					
CX3CL1					
I-TAC/CXCL11					
CCL14					
CCL21					
CCL28					
MCP-1					

MCP-4					
4BB-1					
IP10					
Others:					
Pro-BNP					
CRP					
LDH					
Complement C ₃					
Complement C _{3c}					
Complement C _{3d}					
Complement C ₄					
Complement C _{4c}					
Complement CH ₅₀					
KL-6					
SP-A					
SP-D					

HRCT – High Resolution Computed Tomography of Thorax, CT - Computed Tomography of Thorax, MRI – Magnetic Resonance Imaging, PET – Positron Emission Tomography, CXR - Chest X-ray

The quality of evidence for the reported primary and secondary outcomes will be evaluated according to the GRADE tool. If relevant, additional elements will be analysed separately. We will report if we believe that additional studies will improve the level of evidence.

Discussion

Pulmonary diseases among SLE patients are of importance, but unfortunately it draws little attention. This might be due to the insidious nature of the symptoms and the required extensive diagnostic work-up. Biomarkers are often accessible to rheumatologists, and they could potentially help in the diagnostic work-up of pulmonary diseases among SLE patients. There are reports on associations between pulmonary disease and biomarkers among SLE patients, but we believe that a systemic review on the topic will help to clarify the evidence on the topic, making it easier accessible. This could help clinicians to identify and diagnose pulmonary disease among SLE patients.

Disclosures

HZL, receives funding from Southern Danish University, Region Southern Denmark and The Danish Rheumatism Association. Otherwise the review receives no funding. The sponsors do not have any share in developing or publishing the protocol.

RC: Nil. The Parker Institute, Bispebjerg and Frederiksberg Hospital is supported by a core grant from the Oak Foundation (OCAY-18-774-OFIL).

Funding

Section for Biostatistics and Evidence-Based Research, The Parker Institute, Bispebjerg and Frederiksberg Hospital is supported by a core grant from the Oak Foundation (OCAY-18-774-OFIL).

References

1. Kaul A, Gordon C, Crow MK, Touma Z, Urowitz MB, van Vollenhoven R, et al. Systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2016;2:16039.
2. D'Cruz DP. Systemic lupus erythematosus. *Bmj*. 2006;332(7546):890-4.
3. Quadrelli SA, Alvarez C, Arce SC, Paz L, Sarano J, Sobrino EM, et al. Pulmonary involvement of systemic lupus erythematosus: analysis of 90 necropsies. *Lupus*. 2009;18(12):1053-60.
4. Haupt HM, Moore GW, Hutchins GM. The lung in systemic lupus erythematosus. Analysis of the pathologic changes in 120 patients. *Am J Med*. 1981;71(5):791-8.
5. Tani C, Elefante E, Arnaud L, Barreira SC, Bulina I, Cavagna L, et al. Rare clinical manifestations in systemic lupus erythematosus: a review on frequency and clinical presentation. *Clin Exp Rheumatol*. 2022;40 Suppl 134(5):93-102.
6. Fidler L, Keen KJ, Touma Z, Mittoo S. Impact of pulmonary disease on patient-reported outcomes and patient-performed functional testing in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus*. 2016;25(9):1004-11.
7. Narváez J, Borrell H, Sánchez-Alonso F, Rúa-Figueroa I, López-Longo FJ, Galindo-Izquierdo M, et al. Primary respiratory disease in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus: data from the Spanish rheumatology society lupus registry (RELESSER) cohort. *Arthritis Res Ther*. 2018;20(1):280.
8. Osman HM, Abdel-Nasser AM, Kasem AH, Elameen NF, Omar GM. Pulmonary involvement: A potential independent factor for quality of life in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus*. 2023;32(2):198-206.
9. Svenungsson E, Gunnarsson I, Illescas-Bäckelin V, Trysberg E, Jönsen A, Leonard D, et al. Quick Systemic Lupus Activity Questionnaire (Q-SLAQ): a simplified version of SLAQ for patient-reported disease activity. *Lupus Sci Med*. 2021;8(1).
10. Fanouriakos A, Kostopoulou M, Alunno A, Aringer M, Bajema I, Boletis JN, et al. 2019 update of the EULAR recommendations for the management of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 2019;78(6):736-45.
11. Kondoh Y, Makino S, Ogura T, Suda T, Tomioka H, Amano H, et al. 2020 guide for the diagnosis and treatment of interstitial lung disease associated with connective tissue disease. *Respir Investig*. 2021;59(6):709-40.
12. Kello N, Anderson E, Diamond B. Cognitive Dysfunction in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: A Case for Initiating Trials. *Arthritis Rheumatol*. 2019;71(9):1413-25.
13. Osman HM, Omar GM, Elameen NF, Abdel-Nasser AM. CCL21 and IP10 as serum biomarkers for pulmonary involvement in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus*. 2022;31(6):706-15.
14. Alamoudi OS, Attar SM. Pulmonary manifestations in systemic lupus erythematosus: association with disease activity. *Respirology*. 2015;20(3):474-80.
15. Oki H, Aoki T, Saito K, Yamashita Y, Hanamiya M, Hayashida Y, et al. Thin-section chest CT findings in systemic lupus erythematosus with antiphospholipid syndrome: a comparison with systemic lupus erythematosus without antiphospholipid syndrome. *Eur J Radiol*. 2012;81(6):1335-9.
16. Liberati A, Altman DG, Tetzlaff J, Mulrow C, Gøtzsche PC, Ioannidis JP, et al. The PRISMA statement for reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses of studies that evaluate healthcare interventions: explanation and elaboration. *Bmj*. 2009;339:b2700.
17. Kirkham JJ, Altman DG, Chan AW, Gamble C, Dwan KM, Williamson PR. Outcome reporting bias in trials: a methodological approach for assessment and adjustment in systematic reviews. *Bmj*. 2018;362:k3802.
18. Thompson S, Ekelund U, Jebb S, Lindroos AK, Mander A, Sharp S, et al. A proposed method of bias adjustment for meta-analyses of published observational studies. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2011;40(3):765-77.

The search string for EMBASE

Search results, from "Evidence-based research"

- 1: Islam MA, Khandker SS, et al. R. Immunomodulatory Effects of Diet and Nutrients in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE): A Systematic Review. *Front Immunol.* 2020 Jul 22;11:1477
- 2: Curtiss P, Walker AM, Chong BF. A Systematic Review of the Progression of Cutaneous Lupus to Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. *Front Immunol.* 2022 Mar 11;13
- 3: Kawai K, Yawn BP. Risk Factors for Herpes Zoster: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2017 Dec;92(12):1806-1821.
- 4: Steiger S, Ehreiser L, et al. Biological drugs for systemic lupus erythematosus or active lupus nephritis and rates of infectious complications. Evidence from large clinical trials. *Front Immunol.* 2022 Sep 23;13
- 5: Zhang M, Wang Y, Wang Y, Bai Y, Gu D. Association Between Systemic Lupus Erythematosus and Cancer Morbidity and Mortality: Findings From Cohort Studies. *Front Oncol.* 2022 May 4;12
- 6: Clarke AE, Pooley N, et al. Risk of malignancy in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Semin Arthritis Rheum.* 2021 Dec;51(6):1230-1241
- 7: Liu Z, Cheng R, Liu Y. Evaluation of anifrolumab safety in systemic lupus erythematosus: A meta-analysis and systematic review. *Front Immunol.* 2022 Sep 23;13
- 8: Alexanderson H, Boström C. Exercise therapy in patients with idiopathic inflammatory myopathies and systemic lupus erythematosus - A systematic literature review. *Best Pract Res Clin Rheumatol.* 2020 Apr;34(2):
- 9: Song L, Wang Y, et al. The risks of cancer development in systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Arthritis Res Ther.* 2018 Dec 6;20(1):270.
- 10: Joy GM, Arbiv OA, et. al. Prevalence, imaging patterns and risk factors of interstitial lung disease in connective tissue disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur Respir Rev.* 2023 Mar 8;32(167)
- 11: Moscicki AB, Flowers L, et al. Guidelines for Cervical Cancer Screening in Immunosuppressed Women Without HIV Infection. *J Low Genit Tract Dis.* 2019 Apr;23(2):87-101.
- 12: Tusseau M, Lovšin E, et al. DNASE1L3 deficiency, new phenotypes, and evidence for a transient type I IFN signaling. *J Clin Immunol.* 2022 Aug;42(6):1310-1320.
- 13: Weitkamp K, Feger F, et al. Dyadic Coping in Couples Facing Chronic Physical Illness: A Systematic Review. *Front Psychol.* 2021 Oct 25;12
- 14: Aram K, Patil A, et al.. COVID-19 and exacerbation of dermatological diseases: A review of the available literature. *Dermatol Ther.* 2021 Nov;34(6)
- 15: Ferrari-Souza JP, Pedrotti MT, et al. Endometriosis and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Reprod Sci.* 2023 Apr;30(4):997-1005.

- 16: Bigna JJ, Noubiap JJ, et al. Prevalence and etiologies of pulmonary hypertension in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2017 Dec 8;17(1):183.
- 17: Xia YK, Tu SH, et al. Pulmonary hypertension in systemic lupus erythematosus: a systematic review and analysis of 642 cases in Chinese population. *Rheumatol Int*. 2013 May;33(5):1211-7.
- 18: Wu Q, Liu Y, Wang W, et al. Incidence and prevalence of tuberculosis in systemic lupus erythematosus patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Immunol*. 2022 Jul 22;13:938406.
- 19: Suárez-Avellaneda A, Quintana JH, et al. Systemic lupus erythematosus in the intensive care unit: a systematic review. *Lupus*. 2020 Oct;29(11):1364-1376.
- 20: Bundhun PK, Kumari A, Huang F. Differences in clinical features observed between childhood-onset versus adult-onset systemic lupus erythematosus: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2017 Sep;96(37)
- 21: Zuily S, Domingues V, et al. Antiphospholipid antibodies can identify lupus patients at risk of pulmonary hypertension: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Autoimmun Rev*. 2017 Jun;16(6):576-586.
- 22: Reynaud Q, Lega JC, et al. Risk of venous and arterial thrombosis according to type of antiphospholipid antibodies in adults without systemic lupus erythematosus: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Autoimmun Rev*. 2014 Jun;13(6):595-608.
- 23: Wang J, Qian J, et al. Serological biomarkers as risk factors of SLE-associated pulmonary arterial hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lupus*. 2017 Nov;26(13):1390-1400.
- 24: Qian J, Wang Y, et al. Survival and prognostic factors of systemic lupus erythematosus-associated pulmonary arterial hypertension: A PRISMA-compliant systematic review and meta-analysis. *Autoimmun Rev*. 2016 Mar;15(3):250-7.
- 25: Tessier-Cloutier B, Clarke AE, et al. What investigations are needed to optimally monitor for malignancies in SLE? *Lupus*. 2015 Jul;24(8):781-7.
- 26: Duron L, Cohen-Aubart F, et al. Shrinking lung syndrome associated with systemic lupus erythematosus: A multicenter collaborative study of 15 new cases and a review of the 155 cases in the literature focusing on treatment response and long-term outcomes. *Autoimmun Rev*. 2016 Oct;15(10):994-1000.
- 27: Toledano E, Candelas G, et al. A meta-analysis of mortality in rheumatic diseases. *Reumatol Clin*. 2012 Nov-Dec;8(6):334-41.
- 28: Sun T, Wang J, et al. A systematic review and meta-analysis: effects of glucocorticoids on rheumatoid arthritis and systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann Palliat Med*. 2021 Jul;10(7):7977-7991.
- 29: Chow SL, Chandran V, et al. Prognostic factors for survival in systemic lupus erythematosus associated pulmonary hypertension. *Lupus*. 2012 Apr;21(4):353-64.
- 30: Medlin JL, Hansen KE, et al. Pulmonary manifestations in late versus early systemic lupus erythematosus: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Semin Arthritis Rheum*. 2018 Oct;48(2):198-204.

- 31: Merashli M, Alves J, Ames PRJ. Clinical relevance of antiphospholipid antibodies in systemic sclerosis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Semin Arthritis Rheum.* 2017 Apr;46(5):615-624.
- 32: Antonopoulos CN, Sfyroeras GS, et al. The role of soluble P selectin in the diagnosis of venous thromboembolism. *Thromb Res.* 2014 Jan;133(1):17-24.
- 33: Finsterer J, Aliyev R. Metabolic stroke or stroke-like lesion: Peculiarities of a phenomenon. *J Neurol Sci.* 2020 May 15;412:116726.
- 34: Bruera S, Sreedhar A, et al. Immunosuppression for the treatment of pulmonary hypertension in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus: A systematic review. *Int J Rheum Dis.* 2023 Jun;26(6):1022-1028.
- 35: Shreberk-Hassidim R, Ramot Y, Zlotogorski A. Janus kinase inhibitors in dermatology: A systematic review. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2017 Apr;76(4):745-753.e19.
- 36: Huang X, Jia N, et al. Differences in the Clinical Manifestations and Mortality of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus Onset in Children and Adults: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol.* 2022;183(1):116-126.
- 37: Kronbichler A, Kerschbaum J, Mayer G. The Influence and Role of Microbial Factors in Autoimmune Kidney Diseases: A Systematic Review. *J Immunol Res.* 2015;2015:858027.
- 38: Zia A, Russell J, et al. Markers of coagulation activation, inflammation and fibrinolysis as predictors of poor outcomes after pediatric venous thromboembolism: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Thromb Res.* 2017 Dec;160:1-8.
- 39: Zhang L, Wu H, Zhao M, Lu Q. Identifying the differentially expressed microRNAs in autoimmunity: A systemic review and meta-analysis. *Autoimmunity.* 2020 May;53(3):122-136. doi: 10.1080/08916934.2019.1710135. Epub 2020 Jan 6. PMID: 31902241.
- 40: Aringer M, Burkhardt H, et al. Current state of evidence on 'off-label' therapeutic options for systemic lupus erythematosus, including biological immunosuppressive agents, in Germany, Austria and Switzerland—a consensus report. *Lupus.* 2012 Apr;21(4):386-401.
- 41: Xu T, Zhang G, Lin H, Xie Y, Feng Y, Zhang X, Dong G. Clinical Characteristics and Risk Factors of Diffuse Alveolar Hemorrhage in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Based on Observational Studies. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol.* 2020 dec;59(3):295-303.
- 42: Koh JWH, Ng CH, Tay SH. Biologics targeting type I interferons in SLE: A meta-analysis and systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Lupus.* 2020 Dec;29(14):1845-1853.
- 43: Larsen JB, Hvas CL, Hvas AM. The Lectin Pathway in Thrombotic Conditions-A Systematic Review. *Thromb Haemost.* 2018 Jul;118(7):1141-1166.
- 44: Abdel-Wahab N, Tayar JH, et al. Systematic review of observational studies reporting antiphospholipid antibodies in patients with solid tumors. *Blood Adv.* 2020 Apr 28;4(8):1746-1755.

- 45: Fukushima K, Uchida HA, et al. Silica-associated systemic lupus erythematosus with lupus nephritis and lupus pneumonitis: A case report and a systematic review of the literature. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2022 Feb 18;101(7):e28872.
- 46: Orlandi M, Landini N, et al. Pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis in rheumatic autoimmune diseases: a systematic literature review. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2020 Dec 1;59(12):3645-3656.
- 47: Sobanski V, Lemaire-Olivier A, et al. Prevalence and Clinical Associations of Antiphospholipid Antibodies in Systemic Sclerosis: New Data From a French Cross-Sectional Study, Systematic Review, and Meta- Analysis. *Front Immunol*. 2018 Nov 2;9:2457.
- 48: Reddy HG, Maynes EJ, et al. Utilization of extracorporeal life support for diffuse alveolar damage and diffuse alveolar hemorrhage: A systematic review. *Artif Organs*. 2021 Jun;45(6):559-568.
- 49: Wouters A, Durieux V, et al. Bullous Lupus Under Nivolumab Treatment for Lung Cancer: A Case Report With Systematic Literature Review. *Anticancer Res*. 2019 Jun;39(6):3003-3008.
- 50: Ding Y, Qian J, et al. Immunosuppressive therapy in patients with connective tissue disease-associated pulmonary arterial hypertension: A systematic review. *Int J Rheum Dis*. 2022 sep;25(9):982-990.
- 51: Toya SP, Tzelepis GE. Association of the shrinking lung syndrome in systemic lupus erythematosus with pleurisy: a systematic review. *Semin Arthritis Rheum*. 2009 Aug;39(1):30-7.
- 52: Tryfon S, Papadopoulou E, et al. Clinical and pathophysiological characteristics of valproate-induced pleural effusion. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*. 2021 Oct;59(10):869-876.
- 53: Landman S, van der Horst C, et al. Immune responses to azacytidine in animal models of inflammatory disorders: a systematic review. *J Transl Med*. 2021 Jan 6;19(1):11.
- 54: Young A, Nagaraja V, et al. Update of screening and diagnostic modalities for connective tissue disease-associated pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Semin Arthritis Rheum*. 2019 Jun;48(6):1059-1067.
- 55: Franchi T, Eaton S, et al. The emerging role of immunothrombosis in paediatric conditions. *Pediatr Res*. 2019 Jul;86(1):19-27.
- 56: Wahl DG, Guillemin F, et al. Risk for venous thrombosis related to antiphospholipid antibodies in systemic lupus erythematosus--a meta-analysis. *Lupus*. 1997;6(5):467-73.
- 57: Tamborrini G, Distler O. Neues zur pulmonalen Hypertonie bei Kollagenosen - eine systematische Literaturübersicht [Update in pulmonary hypertension associated with connective tissue diseases - a systematic literature review]. *Dtsch Med Wochenschr*. 2008 Oct;133 Suppl 6:S199-202. German.